

SURVEILLANCE CARD_*Echinococcus granulosus*_Adult parasite detection in wild canids

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	Detection of the adult <i>E. granulosus</i> parasite in wild canids. Convenience sampling of hunted, trapped, road killed and found dead wild canids (wolf, fox, racoon dog) to identify animals infested with adult parasites (intestinal scraping, coprological tests, PCR) of <i>E. granulosus</i> .
2	Surveillance aim	Detection of the introduction of the parasite into new areas and to detect signals for changing patterns and trends over time. If the date and location of samples is recorded, and the sampling frequency is relatively constant over time, in terms of the location and number of samples, they may be used to identify the introduction of the parasite into new geographic regions, and they may be used to identify signals for changing patterns or trends in the population. Because the samples are biased, sample prevalence (the proportion of the sample that tested positive) must be interpreted with caution because it is a biased estimation of the population prevalence. Therefore, care must be taken when interpreting signals based on changing sample prevalence, and all signals should be verified with disease investigations or other studies.
3	Target species and group	Definitive hosts: wild canids including free ranging wolves, foxes, racoon dogs. Wolves are especially important as they prey on sheep, and they can travel hundreds of kilometres, introducing the parasite into new geographic regions.
4	Target sector / production type	Free ranging wild canids.
5	Geographical area covered	Whole country.
6	Age group	All.
7	Sampling point and strategy	Hunter kills, trapped animals, and public reporting of road killed and found dead animals.
8	Sampling time period	Year-round.
9	Sampling matrix	Carcasses and faeces of wild canids.

10	Type of disease indicators	No disease in definitive hosts.
11	Sampling unit	Animal.
12	Allocation of animal groups /animals to sampling	Not applicable.
13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	The sedimentation and flotation technique of faecal samples allows detecting taeniid eggs and worm fragments, followed by the differentiation of the different taeniid parasites by PCR.
14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	The component contributes to case detection, but as this is a biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population (convenience sampling), it cannot be used directly to estimate the system sensitivity. Sensitivity and timeliness are both expected to be improved with higher coverage of the sampling.
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	<i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i> , rabies and vector borne pathogens in wild canids.
18	References	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Romig, T., Dinkel, A., & Mackenstedt, U. (2006). The present situation of echinococcosis in Europe. <i>Parasitology international</i>, 55, S187-S191. 2) https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/publications-data/european-union-one-health-2021-zoonoses-report 3) Otero-Abad B., Torgerson P.R.A (2013) Systematic Review of the Epidemiology of Echinococcosis in Domestic and Wild Animals <i>Plos Neglected Tropical Diseases</i> https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0002249 4) Woolsey I.D., Miller (2021) <i>Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato</i> and <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i>: a review. <i>Research in Veterinary Science</i> 135:517-522 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rvsc.2020.11.010

		<p>5) Trachsel, D., Deplazes, P., & Mathis, A. (2007). Identification of taeniid eggs in the faeces from carnivores based on multiplex PCR using targets in mitochondrial DNA. <i>Parasitology</i>, 134(6), 911-920.</p> <p>6) https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/echinococcosis</p> <p>7) http://atlas.ecdc.europa.eu/public/index.aspx?Dataset=27&HealthTopic=18</p> <p>8) Eckert, J., Gemmell, M. A., Meslin, F. X., Pawlowski, Z. S., & World Health Organization. (2001). WHO/OIE manual on echinococcosis in humans and animals: a public health problem of global concern. World Organisation for Animal Health.</p>
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